

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OMWA****FIRST NAME: SAMUEL SAMSON****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: MSWord Professional 2019 on windows 11 home single language.

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following alternatives best describes Plagiarism?¹

- Plagiarism is the process of using data, ideas, or works without acknowledging the author of that source of information.**
- Plagiarism is not academic fraud.
- Plagiarism is when a content creator uses one or two sentences of existing work crediting the source.
- Plagiarism is only applicable when writing a dissertation.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

2. In undertaking any doctoral research project, a student requires a research proposal.

According to Bloomberg and Volpe (2019), what are the three essential components of a doctoral research proposal?²

- The three components of a research proposal are the title of the research proposal, the literature review and the methodology.
- The three essential components of a research proposal are the introduction to the study, literature review and methodology.**
- The three components of a research proposal are the title of the research proposal, the introduction, and the literature review.
- The main elements of a research proposal are the title of the research proposal, literature review and methodology.

3. What is a Working Hypothesis?³

- A working hypothesis indicates to the readers the aim of the research.
- A working hypothesis is what the researcher wants to test.
- A working hypothesis, in general, is an imaginary answer to a research question proposed by a researcher.**
- A working hypothesis is a method for undertaking research.

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Forth ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publication Ltd, 2019), 205–210.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 30–32.

4. Which of the following options best describes a research argument in academic writing?⁴

- A research argument is a conversation between the researcher and the interested audience.**
- A research argument is a judgement formed by the researcher.
- A research argument is the researcher's view based on the results of his research finding.
- The research argument is how a researcher presents the findings of a study.

5. The qualitative research tradition promotes a deep understanding of a problem, situation or context as viewed from the perspective of the research participants. In qualitative research, a researcher emphasizes on:⁵

- In qualitative research, the emphasis is on exploration, discovery and description.**
- In qualitative research, a researcher is mainly concerned with description, investigation and discovery.
- Qualitative research is more concerned with discovery, exploration and cause-effect.
- In qualitative research, the emphasis is on the investigation, cause-effect, and description.

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 56–57.

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 135.

6. An author must undertake an extensive literature review in academic writing. Which of the following sentence best describes a literature review? ⁶
- The literature review is a mandatory requirement for writing a dissertation.
 - The literature review is a summary presentation of what other scholars have written about a topic.
 - The literature review demonstrates that an author knows what other scholars have written about the research topic.**
 - A literature review does not necessarily have to examine what other scholars have written.
7. Which of the following is a correct in-text citation (Parenthetical citation) according to the Turabian?⁷
- (Mukherjee, 2013).
 - (Mukherjee, 2013, 84-85).
 - (Mukherjee, A. 2013).
 - (Mukherjee 2013, 84–85).**
8. Which part of a dissertation provides an analysis, interpretation, and summary of results or findings?⁸
- Recommendations.

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 206.

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 244.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 288.

- Executive summary.
 - Conclusions.**
 - Discussions.
9. An abbreviation can be written in several forms: an acronym, initialism, contractions, or truncation. Which of the following combination of words represents an initialism?⁹
- AIDS, NATO, BBC and USA.
 - BBC, EU, UK and USA.**
 - BBC, NATO, USA and EU.
 - VOL., CO, INC., and MR.
10. According to Turabian, what is the difference between a bibliography and a reference list?¹⁰
- A reference list is a detailed list of references cited by an author, while a bibliography is placed at the end of a thesis listing all sources cited as footnotes.
 - A reference list is a detailed list of references cited by an author. A bibliography lists sources at the end of the paper and includes every reference cited in a note and other sources consulted but not cited in the body of the text.**
 - A references list is a detailed list of sources cited by the author, while a bibliography is placed at the end of the thesis listing all works mentioned.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, European Union, 2021, 43–44.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis and Dissertations*, 142.

- A reference list lists sources at the end of the paper. It includes every reference cited in a note and other sources consulted but not cited in the body of the text. At the same time, a bibliography is a detailed list of works cited by an author.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Forth ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publication Ltd, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Forth ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. European Union, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.